

Original Article

Auto-contouring of cardiac substructures for Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR): A STOPSTORM.eu consortium study

Luuk H.G. van der Pol^{a,*}, Oliver Blanck^b, Melanie Grehn^b, Tomáš Blazek^c, Lukáš Knybel^c, Brian V. Balgobind^d, Joost J.C. Verhoeff^d, Marcin Miszczyk^{e,f,g}, Sławomir Blamek^h, Sabrina Reichlⁱ, Nicolaus Andratschkeⁱ, Felix Mehrhof^j, Judit Boda-Heggemann^k, Bartłomiej Tomasiak^{h,l}, Stefano Mandija^a, Martin F. Fast^{a,*}

^a Department of Radiotherapy, University Medical Center Utrecht, Utrecht, the Netherlands

^b Department of Radiation Oncology, University Medical Center Schleswig-Holstein, Kiel, Germany

^c Department of Oncology, University Hospital and Faculty of Medicine, Ostrava, Czech Republic

^d Department of Radiation Oncology, Amsterdam UMC Location University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^e Collegium Medicum - Faculty of Medicine, WSB University, Dąbrowa Górnicza, Poland

^f IIRD Radiotherapy and Chemotherapy Department, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, Gliwice, Poland

^g Department of Urology, Comprehensive Cancer Center, Medical University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria

^h Department of Radiotherapy, Maria Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology, Gliwice, Poland

ⁱ Department of Radiation Oncology, University Hospital of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

^j Department for Radiation Oncology, Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Berlin, Germany

^k Department of Radiation Oncology, University Medical Center Mannheim, Medical Faculty Mannheim, University of Heidelberg, Mannheim, Germany

^l Department of Oncology and Radiotherapy, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Gdańsk, Gdańsk, Poland

A B S T R A C T

Background/Purpose: High doses to healthy cardiac substructures (CS) in stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) raise concerns regarding potential treatment-induced cardio-toxicity. However, CS contours are not routinely created, hindering the understanding of the CS dose–effect relationships. To address this issue, the alignment of CS contouring was initiated within the STOPSTORM consortium. In this study, we developed and evaluated auto-contouring models trained to delineate CS and major vessels in ventricular tachycardia (VT) patients.

Methods: Eight centres provided standard treatment planning computed tomography (CT) and/or contrast-enhanced CT datasets of 55 VT patients, each including 16 CS. Auto-contouring models were trained to contour either large structures or small structures. Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), 95 % Hausdorff distance (HD95) and volume ratio (VR) were used to evaluate model performance versus inter-observer variation (IOV) on seven VT patient test cases. Significant differences were tested using the Mann-Whitney *U* test.

Results: The performance on the four chambers and the major vessels (median DSC: 0.88; HD95: 5.8–19.4 mm; VR: 1.09) was similar to the IOV (median DSC: 0.89; HD95: 4.8–14.0 mm; VR: 1.20).

For the valves, model performance (median DSC: 0.37; HD95: 11.6 mm; VR: 1.63) was similar to the IOV (median DSC: 0.41; HD95: 12.4 mm; VR: 3.42), but slightly worse for the coronary arteries (median DSC: 0.33 vs 0.42; HD95: 24.4 mm vs 16.9 mm; VR: 1.93 vs 3.30). The IOV for these small structures remains large despite using contouring guidelines.

Conclusion: CS auto-contouring models trained on VT patient data perform similarly to IOV. This allows for time-efficient evaluation of CS as possible organs-at-risk.

Introduction

Stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation (STAR) is increasingly used to treat ventricular tachycardia (VT), specifically recurrent VT after catheter ablations [1,2]. The most common STAR treatment protocol involves delivering 1x25 Gy to the arrhythmia substrate, with maximum doses reaching up to 40 Gy [2–4]. Applying such high doses to the heart

raises concerns regarding potential treatment-induced cardio-toxicity. Especially, long-term toxicity is yet to be investigated [1,5,6]. Currently, only whole heart dose constraints, originating from thoracic radiotherapy (RT), are used consistently while the use of cardiac substructure (CS) dose constraints varies between institutes [3]. A substantial obstacle to understanding CS dose–effect relationships is the lack of consistent, high-quality delineations. CS are not routinely contoured in

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: L.H.G.vanderpol@umcutrecht.nl (L.H.G. van der Pol), m.f.fast-2@umcutrecht.nl (M.F. Fast).

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clinical practice, as manual contouring is labour-intensive, while knowledge about dose constraints for CS is limited. The CS contouring challenges are compounded in STAR patients who typically suffer from structural heart disease and have implantable cardioverter defibrillators (ICDs) with cardiac leads that induce artefacts on computed tomography (CT) scans [7].

Previously, a manual contouring benchmark study, within the Standardised Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy Of Re-entrant tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary (STOPSTORM) consortium (EU-Horizon-2020 GA No. 945119), was performed [8]. In that study, three example STAR cases were contoured (based on planning CT and contrast-enhanced CT (CECT) scans) by participants from 20 centres. Good agreement was found for large cardiac structures (four chambers and the whole heart), large vessels and other large structures that are commonly contoured in the RT workflow. However, lower agreement was found for smaller structures, like valves and coronary arteries (CA) [9,10].

In this study, we developed and evaluated an auto-contouring tool specifically geared towards CS and major vessel delineations in VT patients using deep learning models trained on a multi-institutional dataset of 55 VT patients.

Methods

This investigation is part of the STOPSTORM project plan [3]. Ethical approval was obtained through the STOPSTORM European observational and prospective registry trial (University Hospital Zurich, Switzerland, BASEC 2021–01730), through the STOPSTORM benchmark study (University of Kiel, Germany, D483/21), and local ethics review (University Medical Center Utrecht).

Eight STOPSTORM.eu consortium centres provided delineations of relevant cardiac and vessel structures in VT patient cases following established guidelines [8]. The delineations included the left atrium (LA), right atrium (RA), left ventricle (LV), right ventricle (RV), aorta, inferior/superior vena cava (IVC/SVC), pulmonary artery (PA), aortic valve (AV), pulmonic valve (PV), mitral valve (MV), tricuspid valve (TV), left main (LM) CA, left anterior descending (LAD) CA, left circumflex (LCX) CA, and right CA (RCA). These contours were created for 55 VT patients, based on 52 RT planning CT scans and 21 CECT scans. Despite the limited number of paired scans being available for training, all but one centre indicated using CECT during manual delineation. In most centres, the CECT was rigidly registered to the planning CT, but two centres indicated using deformable registration after using rigid registration. On average it took observers 120 min to create one full set of contours for a VT patient, while some indicated manual contouring can take up to 4 h. Additional to the VT patient data, planning CT scans and contours (limited to PA/SVC/IVC/Aorta/LA/RA/LV/RV) were available for a single-institutional cohort of 70 lung cancer patients.

Four auto-contouring networks were trained based on this data (all 3D full-resolution nnU-Nets, using version 2 without any post-processing [11]). Each network was a 3D patch-based network, trained for 1000 epochs, using the ensemble model of 5-fold cross-validation: model A included the lung cancer patient data, model B included the VT patient data, and model C was based on the combination of all lung cancer patient and VT patient data. These three models were trained to create delineations for the large CS (four major vessels and four chambers). Additionally model B* was trained, on the VT patient

Table 1

Overview of the data used for training and testing. All images have 512x512 pixels in-plane. Abbreviations: LA = left atrium, RA = right atrium, LV = left ventricle, RV = right ventricle, PA = pulmonary artery, SVC = superior vena cava, IVC = inferior vena cava, AV = aortic valve, PV = pulmonic valve, MV = mitral valve, TV = tricuspid valve, LM = left main, LAD = left anterior descending, LCX = left circumflex, RCA = right coronary artery.

Training data/ Characteristic	Model A Lung cancer	Model B/B* VT	Model C Lung cancer + VT	Test data VT
Number of cases	70	55	125	7
Scan types	CT (70 scans)	CT (52 scans) and CECT (21 scans)	CT (122 scans) and CECT (21 scans)	CT (6 scans) and CECT (4 scans)
Included structures	LA/RA/LV/ RV PA/SVC/ IVC/Aorta	B: LA/RA/LV/ RV PA/SVC/ IVC/Aorta B*: AV/PV/MV/ TV LM/LAD/ LCX/RCA	LA/RA/LV/ RV PA/SVC/ IVC/Aorta	LA/RA/LV/ RV PA/SVC/ IVC/Aorta AV/PV/MV/ TV LM/LAD/ LCX/RCA
Total number of contour sets	70	55	125	100 (27/21/20/ 8/8/8/8 per case)
In-plane resolution	0.79–1.37 mm	0.87–1.56 mm	0.79–1.56 mm	0.63–1.56 mm
Slice thickness Superior-inferior	3 mm 264–510 mm	1–3 mm 200–612 mm	1–3 mm 200–612 mm	0.63–3 mm 268–456 mm
Field-of-View				
Median age (min – max)	70 (36–95)	67 (35–84)	70 (35–95)	68 (54 – 78)
Sex	57.6 % male	87.3 % male	70.4 % male	85.7 % male

data, to only contour the small CS (valves, CA). An overview of the used data can be seen in Table 1.

Model performance was evaluated on seven VT patient cases. Three of these cases were previously delineated by up to 27 STOPSTORM.eu consortium centres [8], while the other four cases were contoured by eight expert (co-authoring) centres. Specifics of this dataset are also displayed in Table 1. Besides CT scans, also CECT scans were available for some of the test cases. Therefore, the performance of each model was evaluated on CT and CECT separately. In these evaluations, the model contours were compared with each manual reference contour. The performance of the four models was evaluated based on Dice similarity coefficient (DSC), 95 % Hausdorff distance (HD95) and volume ratio (VR) using SimpleITK (version 2.2.1) in Spyder (version 5.1.5) [12]. HD95 was calculated as the 95th percentile point of the bidirectional distance matrix between the GT and model contours. The VR was calculated as the volume of the larger contour divided by the volume of the smaller contour to allow a more straightforward comparison of results. Pair-wise comparisons were made between contour sets per test case. Additionally, a consensus contour, created using STAPLE (threshold: 0.5), was also compared to each contour set (both manual reference contours and model contour sets) per test case [13,14].

The values from the comparison of each contour set against either

Fig. 1. Overview of the CT scans of three of the seven VT test patient cases. Red arrows point towards the LVAD and LVAD-induced artefacts, whereas blue arrows point towards ICDs. All images are shown with a window/level setting of 400/40 Hounsfield units. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

auto-segmented contours or the consensus contours were used to create boxplots. Additionally, the results of the comparison between consensus contours and auto-segmented contours were added to the plots as individual dots. Significant differences in performance between each model and the IOV were tested using Mann-Whitney *U* test. Thereafter, p-values were corrected for multiple testing using Bonferroni–Holm correction (MATLAB 2023a [15]) [16]. Furthermore, the performance of the models, retrieved from their comparison against the manual reference contours, were compared to each other.

All VT patients in the training and test set had ICDs and corre-

sponding leads, whereas the lung cancer patient dataset included only one patient with an ICD. The training sets that included VT patients (models B, B* and C) and the test set both had one patient with a left ventricular assistant device (LVAD). The LVAD caused prominent image artefacts which were much more severe compared to the ICD leads and complicated the contouring task. Example CT image slices of three of the test patients are shown in Fig. 1. These images highlight the difference in contrast, image quality and severity of lead artefacts that exist within the dataset.

Fig. 2. Visual examples of model performance on the first test patient. The colour scale indicates what percentage of manual observers contoured a certain pixel.

Fig. 3. DSC boxplot of all 16 structures for the four different models on planning CT scans and the inter-observer variability. Whiskers extend towards 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR), where points further away from the median are considered outliers. The black bar indicates the median inter-observer score, whereas the green and red bars indicate the highest and lowest scores from the one-on-one manual reference contour comparison. Significant differences are indicated with * (p-value < 0.05), ** (p-value < 0.01), and *** (p-value < 0.001) Abbreviations: LAD = left anterior descending, LCX = left circumflex, LM = left main, RCA = right coronary artery. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Results

Models were trained on a 48 GB NVIDIA Quadro RTX 8000 GPU, which took around 80 h per model. Predicting one contour set took around 1.5 min. For models B/B* the total prediction time was 3 min. Visual examples of the performance of all models with respect to the manual contouring consensus is depicted in Fig. 2. The left panel shows failure of model A in creating the SVC but also reveals the lower contouring consistency for the IOV, especially at the superior and inferior ends. The middle panel shows accurate performance of model B and C in creating the LV contour, where model A makes several mistakes. The right panel shows the performance of model B* in contouring the LAD,

where the contour created by the model generally follows the observer consensus. Note, there is only one model contour of the LAD, as models A and C do not create small CS.

Here, we compared the results of the performance (of models, as well as the consensus contours) with respect to individual contours. The results of single-observer contour comparison are outlined in the boxplots of Figs. 3–5 and numerical results can be found in Supplementary files 1. It should be noted that the comparison of the model contours against the consensus contours (dots overlayed on the boxplots) closely resembles the boxplot results (numerical results also available in Supplementary files 1).

The performance of the four different networks and the IOV in terms

Fig. 4. 95 % HD for all 16 structures for the four different models on planning CT scans and the inter-observer variability. Whiskers extend towards 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR), where points further away from the median are considered outliers. The black bar indicates the median inter-observer score, whereas the green and red bars indicate the highest and lowest scores from the one-on-one manual reference contour comparison. Significant differences are indicated with * (p-value < 0.05), ** (p-value < 0.01), and *** (p-value < 0.001). Abbreviations: LAD = left anterior descending, LCX = left circumflex, LM = left main, RCA = right coronary artery. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

of DSC can be seen in Fig. 3. The median DSCs over the four chambers and major vessels for the one-on-one comparison revealed significant underperformance of model A (0.50) with respect to the other models (0.88) and the IOV (0.89). The underperformance of model A can be explained by the absence of leads and lead artefacts in the training data. Interestingly, there is only one consensus score for the LV of model B and model C below the median inter-observer score, which upon inspection was revealed to be the test case with an LVAD. Models B and C perform comparably to the IOV for the large vessels (median DSCs of 0.79 (model B), 0.78 (model C), 0.80 (IOV)). However, in the one-on-one comparison, the median DSC of the IVC from model B was significantly worse compared to the IOV. This is likely explained by the inconsistency of training contours at the inferior end, in combination with the ambiguity of the transition between RA and IVC. The median DSC's over the four

CA for model B* (0.33) was somewhat lower than the IOV (0.42), therein significantly worse for the LAD and LCX. Regarding the valves, model B* (median DSC of 0.37) was similar to the IOV (median DSC of 0.41). Additionally, we found that the overall IOV DSC of small structures increased with higher scan resolution. However, there was no consistent increase for HD95 or VR based on resolution.

Fig. 4 shows the performance of the four networks and the IOV in terms of HD95. These results are similar to those of DSC, with significant underperformance for model A compared to the other methods for the large structures (except the IVC and pulmonary artery. Median HD95 of 11.0 mm for both). While median HD95 for model B (5.8–19.4 mm), C (6.0–11.4 mm) and the IOV (4.8–14.0 mm) were comparable, there were still significant differences. The RA, RV, and LV were significantly better in IOV compared to both model B and C. While the differences were

Fig. 5. Volume ratio for all 16 structures for the four different models on planning CT scans and the inter-observer variability. Whiskers extend towards 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR), where points further away from the median are considered outliers. The black bar indicates the median inter-observer score, whereas the green and red bars indicate the highest and lowest scores from the one-on-one manual reference contour comparison. Significant differences are indicated with * (p-value < 0.05), ** (p-value < 0.01), and *** (p-value < 0.001). Abbreviations: LAD = left anterior descending, LCX = left circumflex, LM = left main, RCA = right coronary artery. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

significant, they are minimal as the largest median HD95 difference for these structures was < 1.6 mm. Both model B and C again had an outlier score for the LV in the comparison against the consensus for the LVAD test case. The HD95 was significantly lower for the IVC of model C and the SVC of model B compared to the IOV. Regarding the valves, there were no significant differences between model B* (median HD95 range: 9.1–14.1 mm) and the IOV (median HD95 range: 9.7–16.8 mm).

The VR (displayed in Fig. 5) over the four chambers was more consistent for models B and C compared to model A and the IOV. Regarding the four chambers and the major vessels, the median VR for model B (1.07–1.57) and C (1.09–1.35) were closer to 1, compared to the IOV (1.12–1.80). These differences were significant for all structures except the LV (model C). The small structures show results similar to DSC and HD95, but significance testing varied: model B* was significantly better for every structure except the LCX. However, it should be noted that when compared against the consensus contours, the CAs and tricuspid valve show results that are more similar to the IOV.

The graphical display and numerical results of the performance of the different models on the CECT test data can be found in [Supplementary files 2 and 3](#) respectively. The performance of model A was significantly worse across most parameters when using CECT scans as input, as its training set did not include any CECT scans. The performance of models B and C was similar to the results obtained when planning CTs were used (Differences in median scores for the large structures were <0.05 (DSC), <2 mm (HD95, except IVC for model B), and <0.06 (VR)). However, DSC significantly increased for the LA (model C) but decreased for the Aorta and IVC (model C). Model B* showed significantly different DSC and VR for the LCX (better with CECT, increasing the median DSC from 0.21 to 0.35 and decreasing the median VR by 1.07). However, the median HD95 of the LAD increased

by 25.9 mm compared to the use of the planning CT. Furthermore, there were no significant differences when comparing the scores that were obtained from comparisons against the consensus contours.

Discussion

In this work, we developed and evaluated auto-contouring models for CS and major vessels in VT patients. Overall, the performance of model B (trained on VT data) and model C (trained on Lung + VT data) were similar and equal to IOV. Model B* performed slightly worse in terms of DSC compared to IOV for the CA but better in terms of VR for the CA and valves. The outcomes of the model B/B* and C are also similar to IOV as presented in other studies [8,17,18]. Furthermore, our method matches or outperforms other CS auto-contouring methods developed for non-VT patients, which are arguably easier to contour due to the absence of lead artefacts and less extreme anatomical variation [19–21]. The performance of model A was significantly worse; models trained on planning CTs from patients with thoracic malignancies are not expected to contour the CT scans of VT patients accurately.

The VT patient data that was used to train the DL networks in this study came from eight different centres, as large single-centre cohorts are scarce due to the rare treatment indication. Data from multiple centres comes with the disadvantage that scans are of different quality in terms of resolution, contrast, and artefacts, which can impact the performance of the DL network on scans from a single centre. However, the advantage is that the created networks can better generalize to different data types, thereby being useful over time and in multiple centres (e.g., different CT scanner vendors or different scanning protocols). Eight different centres supplying data also meant that the delineations were created by eight different observers. Similarly, as for the input scans,

contours from different observers make the networks more robust and generalizable. Nonetheless, the IOV was minimized by supplying contouring guidelines.

Only 18 out of the 55 datasets had paired planning CT and CECT scans available for this study. Therefore, each scan was used as a separate input. This might have introduced redundancy, as some patients had their data entered twice (one CT and one CECT), while the GT delineations were the same. We observed that the network performance differed based on the type of scan that is used as input.

The use of CECT scans instead of planning CT scans, as input for the test set, did not substantially alter the results. The limited performance increase of using CECT scans could be caused by: the limited number of CECT scans for training, the larger number of planning CT scans, or sufficient information in the planning CT to create accurate contours. The latter is most likely the case for the larger structures, although their boundaries might be better defined using CECT scans explaining the small improvement in DSC but larger improvements in HD95 for the four chambers when using CECT scans as test input. Another limitation of the training set is the presence of only one LVAD patient, which is likely the cause for the lower performance on the test case with an LVAD. Nevertheless, the performance is still reasonable (four chamber DSC > 0.80).

The performance on small structures (valves and CA) was equal to other methods but remained poor [19,20]. The performance in this study differs per case as the scan quality and location and severity of artefacts differ. However, agreement between observers or between the model and observers was consistently low across the test cases. GT contours for small structures were less accurate (indicated by median IOV DSC of < 0.50, HD95 > 9.6 mm and VS > 2.7) and therefore performance testing was less reliable. Additional small CS could be added in the future e.g., the sinoatrial node, atrioventricular node and pulmonary veins. One factor potentially influencing the accuracy of contouring small structures is scan resolution. CA are only up to a few mm wide and therefore can be as few as 3 pixels in width, and thus can easily be missed [22]. Similarly, heart valves can be 30–40 mm in diameter but as slice thickness is often 2–3 mm, this is only 10–20 pixels [23]. Thus, small mistakes yield large volumetric differences. Increased scan resolution might help mitigate these effects [24].

Another contribution to the inaccuracies for small structures is blurring due to motion, which is more pronounced for small structures compared to large structures. However, the effect of motion is reduced on CECT as these scans are most often ECG-triggered. Thus, triggered, high-resolution CECT scans might help increase the contouring accuracy of small structures in the future. While localization and accurate contouring are logical goals, it does not resemble the treatment situation. During treatment, blurring due to motion is also present and impacts the received dose on CS for the static planned dose. An interesting future research direction would be assessing the effect of motion on the received dose for CS [25]. Additionally, the impact of contouring variability on received dose could be used to investigate if better contouring accuracy for small CS is required [26]. Furthermore, the precision in dose measurement using the model-created contours should be compared to the range of dose measurement using the manual contours.

Many auto-contouring models, also nnU-Net, have overlap metrics in their loss functions. This means that model training is oriented to get perfect overlap with the GT, which for small structures might differ a lot between observers. Thus, the model becomes less accurate. This is not easily solved with more data as the quality of the data has a large influence on model performance [27,28]. Alternatively, for performance testing, model outcomes of small contours can be scored based on acceptability, rather than comparing them against GT contours [29–32]. While these methods can help with grading model performance, they cannot improve the training of the model itself. Model performance for small structures might increase when using alternative metrics for training. Alternatively, a team of observers from different centres and backgrounds could be gathered to increase the consensus of contouring

[8]. Other studies which also employed or even developed contouring guidelines show similar high IOV, but CT scans for VT patients are specifically made for cardiac visualisation and thus might lead to better consensus [9,10,17].

The trained auto-contouring models are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13752275>). These networks can be used to create CS contours quickly, allowing retrospective dosimetric analysis to be done. This is an essential step towards the determination of dose–effect relationships for CS in VT patients treated with STAR. Furthermore, the CS contours could be incorporated into treatment planning once clear constraints are developed. However, it must be noted that these current CS auto-contouring networks are for research purposes only. Clinical implementation is desired in the long term.

Conclusion

We have shown that auto-contouring models trained with data from VT patients can create CS contours with accuracy that matches manual observers. An auto-contouring model, trained on data from patients with thoracic malignancies, without cardiac devices, proved insufficient to accurately contour CS in VT patients. Additionally, auto-contouring massively reduces the time it takes to contour. However, the contour variation of valves and CA's remains large.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luuk H.G. van der Pol: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Oliver Blanck:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Melanie Grehn:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Tomáš Blazek:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Lukáš Knybel:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Brian V. Balgobind:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Joost J.C. Verhoeff:** . **Marcin Miszczyk:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Slawomir Blamek:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Sabrina Reichl:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Nicolaus Andratschke:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Felix Mehrhof:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Judit Boda-Heggemann:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Bartłomiej Tomasik:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Stefano Mandija:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Martin F. Fast:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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